

MNDO Optimized Molecular Geometries of Some Pyrimidine and Purine Derivatives

S. AL-RESAYES*, K. AL-FARHAN, M. MONSHI and A. A. HASANEIN

Department of Chemistry, King Saud University, P.O. Box 2455, Riyadh 11451, Saudi Arabia

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Heats of formation, ionization potentials, dipole moments and molecular geometries have been calculated for some pyrimidine and purine derivatives using the MNDO method. The results are compared with calculated values using other methods and available experimental values.

The crystal structures of nucleic acid bases and their intermolecular complexes have been the subject of several investigations¹⁻⁴. The structures of the different studied compounds have been elucidated in most cases using X-ray¹, electron diffraction², neutron powder diffraction³ and neutron single crystal diffraction⁴. On the other hand a variety of theoretical methods have been used to calculate different one-electron properties, tautomerism and molecular geometries of different pyrimidine and purine bases⁵⁻⁸. Some of these calculations⁵ used different semi-empirical MO methods while others⁶⁻⁸ used different extended basis set ab initio level calculation.

In the present work we report the results of MNDO optimized geometries for different pyrimidine and purine derivatives.

Method of calculation :

A detailed description of the MNDO method has been given by Dewar and his group⁹⁻¹¹ and we only point out here the main features and basic approximations of the method. The MNDO method is an NDDO-based semiempirical SCF-MO treatment of all valence electrons in closed-shell systems. The various terms in the MNDO Fock-matrix were evaluated⁹ using parametric functions which contain adjustable parameters characteristic of individual atoms. To obtain the best forms for these parametric functions and the best values for the parameters in these functions, a non-linear least-squares iterative optimization technique was adopted⁹. The one-center terms W_{μ} , $\langle \mu\mu|\mu\mu \rangle$, and $\langle \mu\nu|\mu\nu \rangle$ were evaluated as in the MINDO/3 method¹². The two-center repulsion integrals were calculated first in a local coordinate system and then transformed to the molecular coordinate system using the Klopman's approximation¹³. The core-electron attractions, the resonance integrals and the core-core repulsions were evaluated using the expressions,

$$U_{b,\mu\nu} = Z_b^* \langle \mu\nu | S^b S^b \rangle \quad (\mu \text{ and } \nu \text{ are on atom } a) \quad (1)$$

$$\beta_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{2} (\beta_{\mu}^a + \beta_{\nu}^b) S_{\mu\nu} \quad (\mu \text{ on } a \text{ and } \nu \text{ on } b) \quad (2)$$

$$CR_{ab} = Z_a^* Z_b^* \langle S^a S^a | S^b S^b \rangle [1 + f(R_{ab})] \quad (3)$$

The overlap integrals $S_{\mu\nu}$ were evaluated analytically over STO's with orbital exponents treated as adjustable parameters and the parameter β_{μ}^a was taken characteristic

of the AO μ of the a'th atom. The function $f(R_{ab})$ was adopted the following empirical expression⁹.

$$f(R_{ab}) = [y' \exp(-\alpha_a R_{ab}) + \exp(-\alpha_b R_{ab})] \quad (4)$$

where α_s are adjustable parameters, and for N-H and O-H atomic pairs expressions (3) and (4) were slightly modified.

Calculations have been performed using the QCPE program no. QCMP002 which is a modification of the program QCPE 353 for use on IBM-PC and compatible systems. A 386-40 MHz IBM compatible PC with Math coprocessor was used.

Results and Discussion

The molecular structure and atom numbering of the pyrimidine and purine derivatives studied here are shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

Fig. 1. Numbering of pyrimidine and its derivatives.

Fig. 2. Numbering of purine and its derivatives.

Table 1 reports the MNDO calculated heats of formation, ionization potentials, dipole moments and net atomic charges of the ring nitrogens. The molecular first ionization potentials are estimated usually as minus the orbital energy of the highest occupied MO. It is worth noting that there is a lack of the experimental heats of formation and also ionization potentials for the systems studied here. However, it is well established based on MNDO applications to a great variety of molecular systems^{11,14-17} that MNDO calculated heats of formation and ionization potentials are quite close to the experimental values. Particularly for nitrogen containing compounds, the MNDO results¹⁵⁻¹⁷ are superior to the MINDO/3 ones in many respects, although the parameters to be adjusted in the MNDO method are considerably fewer than in the MINDO/3 method. Table 1 compares the MNDO calculated values with the experimental data^{18,19}. The mean absolute error in MNDO calculated dipole moments is estimated to be 0.47 D. This value is larger than that found by Nanda and Jug¹⁵ for molecules with first row atoms (0.35 D). However, their value is based on the comparison of MNDO calculated dipole moments for 49 compounds while our value is calculated for only 7 available experimental dipole moments.

The MNDO calculated net atomic charges on the ring nitrogen atoms only are given in Table 1 rather than giving the values for all the atoms in the molecule. Early applications of the MNDO method¹⁰ has shown that MNDO cal-

culated net atomic charges are usually similar to the corresponding STO-3G ab initio calculated values. In the hetero-systems studied here, the MNDO calculated net charges have shown some general trends. Substitution of a chlorine atom or a methyl group for a hydrogen atom at a center makes the net atomic charge of that center more positive.

TABLE 1—MNDO CALCULATED HEATS OF FORMATION, IONIZATION POTENTIALS, DIPOLE MOMENTS AND NET ATOMIC CHARGES

Compd no.	ΔH_f kcal mol ⁻¹	IP eV	μ D	q_N			
				N(1)	N(3)	N(7)	N(9)
1	34.9	10.37	2.01(2.15) ^c	-0.271	-0.271	-	-
2	21.7	10.88	0.76(1.09) ^c	-0.250	-0.250	-	-
3	16.6	10.99	2.15(2.34) ^c	-0.219	-0.216	-	-
4	24.4	9.82	2.02	-0.228	-0.225	-	-0.220
5	-33.7	9.60	1.56	-0.333	-0.315	-0.256	-
6	-64.9	9.94	4.12(4.16) ^d	-0.359	-0.408	-	-
7	-148.2	10.25	3.12	-0.346	-0.405	-	-
8	59.5	9.57	3.11(4.32) ^c	-0.300	-0.260	-0.188	-0.256
9	53.4	9.79	4.30(5.34) ^c	-0.282	-0.252	-0.173	-0.255
10	43.5	10.12	3.69(3.38) ^c	-0.251	-0.220	-0.133	-0.232
11 ^a	8.1	8.84(7.80) ^b	5.24	-0.382	-0.320	-0.149	-0.228
12 ^a	2.9	9.05	5.65	-0.384	-0.323	-0.107	-0.213
13	-38.2	9.30	6.47	-0.419	-0.336	-0.133	-0.254
14	-42.9	9.50	5.82	-0.419	-0.336	-0.093	-0.235

^aMNDO calculated atomic charge on the amino group nitrogen is -0.261.

^bRef. 22. ^cRef. 18. ^dRef. 19.

Tables 2-8 compare the MNDO calculated bond lengths and bond angles with experimental values. Full geometry optimization has been performed for both pyrimidine (1) and purine (8). The MNDO method predicted that both systems are completely planar. In case of purine, a deviation of only 0.2° has been calculated for the hydrogen atom on N(9). We therefore retained the pyrimidine and purine skeletons planar in their studied derivatives. A theoretical study of the basis set dependence of calculated one-electron properties and molecular geometries⁶ confirmed that the planar geometry of the dioxo tautomer of uracil (6) corresponds to a minimum structure at all basis sets applied⁶. Also an ab initio MP2 study of guanine⁸ using the standard 6-31G* basis set predicted that the fully optimized guanine stabilized by as much as 1.6 kcal mol⁻¹ compared to the completely planar molecule while a geometry with planar ring including the amino group nitrogen atom but non-planar amino group hydrogens is stabilized by as much as 1.3 kcal mol⁻¹ compared to the completely planar molecule. Based on the above findings we have included the amino group nitrogen atom in the molecular plane while the dihedral angle between the plane including the amino group nitrogen and hydrogens and the molecular plane (ϕ) has been taken as an optimization parameter. The MNDO calculated values for this angle has been found to be 28.90°, 23.53°, 28.15° and 27.72° for compounds 4, 5, 11 and 12 respectively. The errors calculated as the difference between the MNDO calculated parameter and its experimental value for each compound are given in Tables 2-8.

TABLE 2—MNDO CALCULATED BOND LENGTHS FOR COMPOUNDS 1-5*

Bond	1		2		3		4		5	
	r	Δr	r	Δr	r	Δr	r	Δr	r	Δr
1-2	1.357	0.037	1.359	0.039	1.355	0.035	1.357	0.037	1.367	0.047
2-3	1.0358	0.038	1.358	0.038	1.356	0.036	1.356	0.036	1.366	0.046
3-4	1.352	0.032	1.347	0.027	1.351	0.031	1.344	0.024	1.361	0.041
4-5	1.410	0.050	1.412	0.052	1.411	0.051	1.425	0.065	1.430	0.070
5-6	1.408	0.048	1.411	0.051	1.412	0.052	1.426	0.066	1.416	0.056
6-1	1.353	0.013	1.348	0.027	1.350	0.031	1.344	0.025	1.355	0.055
2-7	1.098	0.098	1.098	0.098	1.733	-0.052	1.097	0.097	1.392	0.072
4-8	1.095	0.095	1.742	-0.043	1.739	-0.046	1.746	-0.039	1.343	0.131
5-9	1.088	0.088	1.087	0.087	1.088	0.088	1.410	0.090	1.746	-0.039
6-10	1.095	0.095	1.742	-0.043	1.738	-0.047	1.744	-0.041	1.513	0.043
9-11							1.007	0.007		
7-15									1.000	0.000
8-16									0.950	0.000
10-11									1.110	0.090

*r is the MNDO calculated bond length; $\Delta r = r(\text{MNDO}) - r(\text{exptl})$.

TABLE 3—MNDO CALCULATED BOND ANGLES FOR COMPOUNDS 1-5*

Angle	1		2		3		4		5	
	θ	$\Delta\theta$								
1-2-3	125.08	-2.92	124.17	-3.83	126.50	1.00	123.56	-2.44	126.09	3.09
2-3-4	117.44	3.44	117.47	3.47	115.74	0.74	117.97	2.97	115.78	0.78
3-4-5	121.27	-4.73	123.03	-1.97	123.28	-1.72	123.40	-1.10	121.73	-2.27
4-5-6	117.50	4.50	114.90	1.90	115.41	1.91	113.76	-1.24	118.31	0.31
5-6-1	121.20	-4.31	122.95	-3.09	122.77	-1.37	122.95	-0.08	119.68	2.23
6-1-2	117.51	4.02	117.49	4.03	116.30	-0.06	118.37	1.90	118.42	-4.13
1-2-7	117.47	1.47	117.96	1.96	116.71	-0.54	118.25	1.25	117.04	-1.46
5-4-8	122.14	5.14	121.35	4.35	121.53	4.53	122.76	4.51	126.58	8.58
4-5-9	121.23	-2.27	122.56	-0.94	122.15	-1.35	123.19	0.69	119.91	-1.09
5-6-10	122.20	5.2	121.52	4.52	121.74	4.74	123.00	6.00	125.93	8.43
5-9-11							112.86	-2.14		
2-7-15									115.72	0.72
4-8-16									113.90	7.90
6-10-13									111.20	1.20
ϕ							28.9		23.53	

 θ : MNDO calculated bond angle; $\Delta\theta = \theta(\text{MNDO}) - \theta(\text{exptl})$.

TABLE 4—MNDO CALCULATED BOND LENGTHS AND BOND ANGLES FOR COMPOUNDS 6, 7*

Bond	6		7		Angle	6		7	
	r	Δr	r	Δr		θ	$\Delta\theta$	θ	$\Delta\theta$
1-2	1.42	0.02	1.42	0.02	1-2-3	115.18	0.68	115.47	0.97
2-3	1.40	0.00	1.40	0.00	2-3-4	125.11	-0.89	124.77	-1.23
3-4	1.43	0.03	1.42	0.02	3-4-5	114.74	-0.76	114.99	-0.51
4-5	1.48	0.02	1.48	0.02	4-5-6	121.37	2.07	121.89	2.59
5-6	1.36	0.02	1.37	0.03	5-6-1	120.14	-1.97	118.91	-3.5
6-1	1.40	0.00	1.40	0.01	6-1-2	123.46	1.17	123.97	1.68
1-7	1.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	6-1-7	118.30	-2.70	119.80	-1.20
2-8	1.23	0.02	1.23	0.02	1-2-8	121.40	-2.40	121.27	-2.53
3-9	1.01	0.01	1.01	0.01	2-3-9	116.36	-1.54	116.57	-1.33
4-10	1.23	0.02	1.22	0.01	3-4-10	117.76	-2.44	118.09	-2.11
5-11	1.09	0.02	1.09	0.02	4-5-11	117.40	-0.80	115.84	-2.36
6-12	1.09	0.02	1.51	0.03	5-6-12	123.94	1.14	122.11	2.11
12-13			1.23	-0.01	6-12-13			124.89	1.89
12-14			1.36	0.06	6-12-14			116.32	-0.68
14-15			0.95	0.00	12-14-15			115.53	10.53

* $\Delta r = r(\text{MNDO}) - r(\text{exptl})$; $\Delta\theta = \theta(\text{MNDO}) - \theta(\text{exptl})$.

8. The mean absolute error in bond lengths (in Å units) are calculated to be 0.059, 0.051, 0.047, 0.048, 0.053, 0.015 and 0.017 for pyrimidine and its derivatives, that is compounds 1-7 respectively. For purine and its derivatives 8-14, the corresponding values are calculated to be 0.048, 0.043, 0.038, 0.047, 0.046, 0.061 and 0.061 Å respectively.

For bond angles the calculated mean absolute errors are 3.8°, 3.01°, 1.8°, 2.21°, 3.25°, 1.55° and 2.35° for the pyrimidine derivatives 1-7 respectively. The corresponding values for purine and its derivatives are calculated to be 1.95°, 2.11°, 2.13°, 2.49°, 2.3°, 2.7° and 2.9° for compounds 8-14 respectively. These results indicate that the MNDO

calculated molecular geometries are good enough for most chemical purposes³. A comparison for compounds of first row elements by Nanda and Jug¹⁶ found mean absolute errors of 0.013–0.020 Å in bond lengths and of 2.4–2.9° in bond angles for the MNDO method. Also, Stewart²⁰ found mean absolute errors in bond lengths and angles of 0.054 Å and 4.3° for MNDO, 0.050 Å and 3.3° for AM1 and 0.036 Å and 3.9° for PM3 methods. It is worthwhile that a thorough investigation²¹ using ab initio methods found the following mean absolute errors in bond lengths and angles 0.054, 0.016, 0.017, 0.014 Å and 2.3°, 3.8°, 3.3°, 1.5° for AH_n molecules using STO-3G, 3-21G, 3-21G* and 6-31G* respectively. For bonds between nonhydrogens and angles not involving hydrogen in molecules with first and second row elements only, the corresponding values were found to be 0.029, 0.029, 0.016 Å and 1.3°, 1.0°, 0.9° using STO-3G, 3-21G and 3-21G* ab initio calculations respectively. Comparing our calculated values of the mean absolute errors for the systems studied here with ab initio results²⁰ indicates that a choice of the MNDO method for calculating molecular geometries is generally satisfactory.

TABLE 5—MNDO CALCULATED BOND LENGTHS FOR COMPOUNDS 8-10

Bond	8		9		10	
	<i>r</i>	Δr	<i>r</i>	Δr	<i>r</i>	Δr
1-2	1.37	0.02	1.37	0.02	1.37	0.02
2-3	1.35	0.03	1.35	0.03	1.35	0.03
3-4	1.36	0.02	1.36	0.02	1.36	0.02
4-5	1.44	0.04	1.44	0.04	1.44	0.04
5-6	1.42	0.03	1.41	0.02	1.41	0.02
6-1	1.34	0.01	1.34	0.01	1.34	0.01
5-7	1.40	0.02	1.40	0.02	1.40	0.02
7-8	1.33	-0.01	1.33	-0.01	1.33	-0.01
8-9	1.41	0.10	1.41	0.10	1.41	0.10
2-10	1.10	0.10	1.10	0.10	1.74	-0.05
6-11	1.10	0.10	1.74	-0.05	1.73	-0.06
8-12	1.09	0.09	1.09	0.09	1.72	-0.07
9-13	1.00	0.05	1.00	0.05	1.00	0.05

* $\Delta r = r(\text{MNDO}) - r(\text{exptl.})$

TABLE 6—MNDO CALCULATED BOND ANGLES FOR COMPOUNDS 8-10*

Angle	8		9		10	
	θ	$\Delta\theta$	θ	$\Delta\theta$	θ	$\Delta\theta$
1-2-3	126.26	-2.24	126.19	-2.31	127.77	-0.73
2-3-4	113.54	0.14	113.62	0.22	112.63	-0.77
3-4-5	124.61	1.51	124.90	1.80	125.06	1.96
4-5-6	116.71	-1.79	115.77	-2.73	115.95	-2.55
5-6-1	118.61	-0.46	119.76	0.69	119.72	0.65
6-1-2	120.26	2.83	119.76	2.33	118.87	1.44
4-5-7	109.40	3.90	109.53	4.03	109.79	4.29
5-7-8	105.87	-0.63	105.74	-0.76	104.70	-1.80
7-8-9	112.33	-1.77	112.41	-1.69	113.80	-0.30
8-9-4	106.62	2.04	106.67	2.09	105.76	1.18
9-4-5	105.79	-3.53	105.65	-3.67	105.76	1.18
3-2-10	117.29	1.54	117.55	1.80	116.59	-3.41
5-6-11	123.53	3.08	123.78	3.78	123.90	3.9
7-8-12	125.79	2.84	125.72	2.77	125.12	5.12
8-9-13	126.77	-0.93	126.79	-0.91	127.23	-0.47

* $\Delta\theta = \theta(\text{MNDO}) - \theta(\text{exptl.})$

TABLE 7—MNDO CALCULATED BOND LENGTHS FOR COMPOUNDS 11-14*

Bond	11		12		13		14	
	<i>r</i>	Δr						
1-2	1.39	0.01	1.39	0.01	1.41	0.05	1.41	0.05
2-3	1.33	0.00	1.34	0.01	1.42	0.07	1.42	0.07
3-4	1.38	0.02	1.38	0.02	1.38	0.04	1.38	0.04
4-5	1.42	0.04	1.42	0.04	1.41	0.02	1.41	0.02
5-6	1.45	0.03	1.45	0.03	1.46	0.02	1.46	0.02
6-1	1.45	-0.36	1.45	-0.36	1.44	0.07	1.44	0.07
5-7	1.39	0.00	1.40	0.01	1.39	0.05	1.39	0.05
7-8	1.34	0.03	1.33	0.02	1.34	0.01	1.34	0.01
8-9	1.41	0.03	1.41	0.03	1.42	0.10	1.41	0.09
4-9	1.38	0.00	1.38	0.00	1.38	0.13	1.39	0.14
2-10	1.41	0.07	1.41	0.07	1.23	0.02	1.23	0.02
1-11	1.00	0.00	1.01	0.01	1.01	0.11	1.01	0.11
6-12	1.22	-0.01	1.22	-0.01	1.22	0.01	1.22	0.01
8-13	1.09	0.09	1.72	-0.07	1.08	0.08	1.72	-0.07
9-14	1.00	0.05	1.00	0.05	0.99	0.09	1.00	0.10
3-15	-	-	-	-	1.00	0.10	1.00	0.10
10-16	1.01	0.01	1.01	0.01	-	-	-	-

* $\Delta r = r(\text{MNDO}) - r(\text{exptl.})$

TABLE 8—MNDO CALCULATED BOND ANGLES FOR COMPOUNDS 11-14*

Angle	11		12		13		14	
	θ	$\Delta\theta$	θ	$\Delta\theta$	θ	$\Delta\theta$	θ	$\Delta\theta$
1-2-3	124.48	1.18	124.66	1.36	116.81	-7.19	116.80	-7.2
2-3-4	113.62	-8.58	113.31	-8.89	118.63	5.63	118.67	5.67
3-4-5	126.70	-1.70	126.92	-1.48	124.21	0.21	124.15	0.15
4-5-6	119.97	0.77	120.17	0.97	120.73	-3.27	120.76	-3.24
5-6-1	110.74	-1.45	110.48	-1.71	111.82	4.19	111.80	4.17
6-1-2	124.49	9.78	124.47	9.76	127.81	0.44	127.82	0.45
4-5-7	109.72	-0.88	110.43	-0.17	109.97	1.97	110.25	2.25
5-7-8	106.06	2.26	104.69	0.89	105.89	-0.11	104.85	-1.15
7-8-9	111.47	-2.53	112.82	-1.18	111.47	3.47	112.85	4.85
8-9-4	106.57	1.39	105.95	0.77	106.25	-6.05	105.40	-6.90
9-4-5	106.19	-0.23	106.11	-0.31	106.42	0.73	106.65	0.96
3-2-10	118.50	-2.10	118.02	-2.58	120.03	2.03	119.96	1.96
2-1-11	118.03	0.63	118.26	0.86	115.01	-1.99	115.07	-1.93
5-6-12	131.92	3.12	132.12	3.32	130.42	3.42	130.28	3.28
7-8-13	126.21	3.21	125.81	2.81	126.52	0.52	126.03	0.03
8-9-14	126.82	-0.58	126.88	-0.52	126.34	1.84	126.62	2.12
2-10-16	113.09	-1.91	113.41	-1.59	-	-	-	-
4-3-15	-	-	-	-	121.48	-3.02	121.51	-2.99
f	28.15	-	27.72	-	-	-	-	-

* $\Delta\theta = \theta(\text{MNDO}) - \theta(\text{exptl.})$

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